

PROBLEMS TO LEARN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the problems that learners confront while learning new languages. Experienced teachers know what difficulties most often arise for students studying foreign languages. Often they are not identified immediately, but some time after the start of classes, which makes correcting deficiencies more difficult, so it is better to practice correctly from the beginning to avoid typical problems.*

Key words: *languages, troubles, solutions, understanding, methods.*

ПРОБЛЕМЫ С ИЗУЧЕНИЕМ ЯЗЫКОВ

Аннотация. *В этой статье рассматриваются проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются учащиеся при изучении новых языков. Опытные преподаватели знают, какие трудности чаще всего возникают у студентов, изучающих иностранные языки. Часто они выявляются не сразу, а через некоторое время после начала занятий, что затрудняет исправление недостатков, поэтому лучше правильно практиковаться с самого начала, чтобы избежать типичных проблем.*

Ключевые слова: *языки, проблемы, решения, понимание, методы.*

INTRODUCTION

When studying English, it happens that a person has a good command of theory, but “floats” in colloquial speech, that is, he does not know how to apply his knowledge in practice. This happens mainly when teaching using the old model, in which most of the time is devoted to vocabulary and grammar. To avoid this, it is better to study using a progressive method - communicative, which is used by modern online schools. Its essence is to primarily focus on active vocabulary and overcoming the language barrier. To this end, most of the lesson is usually devoted not to memorizing the rules, but to direct speech by the student.

Methods

There are some popular methods of teaching languages which can ease students' encountering problems in the period of learning new languages:

Standard. It is most common in schools and universities, despite the fact that it shows little effectiveness in comparison with other teaching methods. This technique is a program that is mostly stuffed with working with grammar. The basis of training is performing exercises based on learned rules. As a rule, speaking and listening comprehension is not easy for students.

Methods of studying with native speakers. As noted above, this technique helps students avoid typical mistakes in pronunciation and not adopt the accent of a non-native speaker teacher. But when communicating with a person from a different language background, attention is concentrated on establishing contact with him, mental activity is aimed at listening to the words of the teacher, trying to understand him (which can be very difficult at first).

Matrix method. This is by far the most effective teaching method. The essence of this approach is that first of all a person must learn to perceive a foreign language by ear (just as children learn a language without knowing the rules of grammar). For this purpose, the program includes listening to dialogues and texts in English, which the creator called the matrix.

Experts call the matrix method of teaching revolutionary in learning English, since it is based on the subconscious abilities of a person and the learning process is easy and interesting.

Based on the above, we can conclude that many people face difficulties in learning English, the main thing is to continue learning, don't quit halfway, and the result will not be long in coming.

Results

In the modern world, knowledge of foreign languages, especially English, helps in many areas of life. For example, it is impossible to learn all languages, but knowing English, you can begin to comfortably travel to different countries and communicate with representatives of their peoples. Knowledge of the English language allows you to enrich yourself culturally by reading or watching films in the original. In a large company, a person who speaks English has more opportunities when promoting or getting a new job in an international company. It is English that is the official language for negotiations in such international organizations as the European Union and the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC), the UN General Assembly, the European Security Union, UNESCO, NATO. Even on the Internet, according to open sources, 54% of information is in English.

However, despite the fact that in most cases the study of foreign languages begins in the second grade and lasts approximately 8–10 years, many people are still unable to master the speech skills and abilities to freely participate in communications or familiarize themselves with written sources of information. This happens due to a number of psychological and pedagogical conditions that either contribute to the successful learning of the English language, or, on the contrary, are the main reason for ignorance of it.

Despite the age at which learning English begins, mistakes that are made during learning can be divided into three main types:

- psychological;
- methodological;
- grammatical.

Psychological mistakes include: incorrect goal setting and striving for the ideal - fear of making mistakes, lack of self-discipline. At any age, even at a very young age, it is necessary to choose the right goal for which a person wants to learn English. For example, in order to start traveling or go on vacation to another country, the need to work with foreign partners may be a mandatory requirement for moving up the career ladder in a company or when applying for a dream job, or just a dream to master another language. Not all people are perfectionists, but many have a fear of making a mistake, saying something wrong or seeming funny because of their accent, so they use simple speech clichés or stop practicing after reaching a certain level, which interferes with further development and development in learning English.

Practice is the main component of any educational process. In the process of mastering any skill, including the English language, an important role is played by a teacher or mentor, who

builds learning systematically, moving from simple to more complex. Therefore, it is important to try to develop self-discipline in yourself so as not to miss classes or systematically study on your own. The next type of errors is methodological: it is important to choose a teaching method based on your individual characteristics.

For example, how do you feel more comfortable studying - in a group or individually; online or offline; How do you perceive information more effectively - visually or auditorily? And one of the main points is that it is necessary to develop all skills at once (reading, speaking, writing, listening). In this way, you will be able to build your learning more effectively, for example, in order to speak well, you need to listen a lot - listening, and reading will allow you to start writing correctly.

The main mistake that relate to methodological ones:

- concentration on grammar;
- only reading;
- only words;
- insufficient repetition of the studied material;
- ignoring correct pronunciation;
- lack of practice of communicating with a native speaker.

Incorrect use of prepositions, you need to clearly understand and understand: in what situations they are necessary, and where their use would be incorrect.

One of the most important factors in mastering most skills is the teacher and his ability to choose the right methodology for both children and adults. However, it is worth understanding that people who go to learn English as adults most often pursue specific goals. An example of the most common goals was indicated at the beginning of the article. Therefore, it is necessary to take these goals into account and build a learning process that will be aimed at achieving them. The teacher must carefully select or develop methods, and sometimes during the lesson, adjust activities that will help students clearly imagine how and in what situation the acquired knowledge can be applied in practice.

Thus, two key features can be identified when learning English by adults, which allow them to overcome most of the main difficulties in mastering the skills that are necessary for learning a foreign language:

- 1) Learning should begin with the activation of past experience in a new situation.
- 2) It is necessary throughout the entire training to update knowledge as applicable in life, significant for a specific situation, with a gradual increase in the volume of material.

Therefore, an English teacher, when teaching his students, should be guided by the following goals:

- To convey to the student the necessary knowledge so that with their help he can use the English language as a means of international communication.
- To create in the student such foreign language competence that will allow him to successfully achieve his goals, which led him to study a foreign language, in this case, English.

Discussion

While learning new languages, such as English, students face some difficulties which can be solved by certain measures recommended by teachers.

Lack of understanding of English speech by ear

Another difficulty stemming from lack of practice. English teachers recommend introducing the language little by little into your life, and in addition to courses:

- listen to songs in English, trying to understand the lyrics;
- watch films with subtitles, not dubbed;
- communicate more with native speakers or similar students.

Gradually, listening to speech will become natural and will no longer cause difficulties.

Constantly forgetting English words

The key to successful learning is regular repetition of what you have learned. If you study once a week, it is not surprising that it will be difficult to remember the vocabulary. The best option is to fluently re-read new words and their translations at least once every two days, as well as make up phrases with them. If immediately after learning new words are used in dialogues, they will replenish the active vocabulary and it will not be easy to forget them.

A useful exercise is not just to read the words, trying to remember them, but to write them down in a notebook with your hands. Even though most of us no longer use anything other than a laptop or computer to learn languages, motor memory matters quite a lot. Even at school, we were often surprised: what was written down in the notes did not need to be repeated again, but what we tried to remember by ear disappeared from our heads. Another example is cheat sheets, which were not encouraged in exams, but teachers still recommended compiling them, knowing that this contributed to the assimilation of information.

Mixing information in the head

This problem can only be solved with time and hard training. Indeed, the English language is complex in structure (more complex than Russian, which has only three main tenses), but gradually with constant practice this problem will also go away.

Another reason for confusion about tenses may be trying to learn them all at once. In fact, there is no need for this, even if you are traveling to an English-speaking country: even if you express yourself simply, using only a few tenses - past, present and future - native speakers will understand you. In learning English, consistency and gradualism are important - students move from simple to complex, without starting a new topic until the previous one has been properly mastered.

Inability to think in English

Thinking in a foreign language means not doing extra work in your head to translate what you heard and transform the answer, but to formulate an answer right away, perceiving the interlocutor's remark as it was spoken. This is a very useful skill that saves energy and time, and also promotes mutual understanding.

The ability to think in English is developed through practice. Try to speak, write, participate in dialogues with your "colleagues" in your studies - over time, this skill will develop if you work on it regularly.

All problems that arise when learning English or another foreign language can be easily solved with the right approach to the learning process. If you have difficulties, it is best to contact your teacher and ask him for advice on what to do to overcome the difficulty.

The relevance of this topic is determined by the fact that today more and more teachers note certain problems in learning English and mastering the material. Students often refer to language inability in such situations. But there are cases when a person knows one or even two languages, however, is not able to master a third. In this case, the reason may be the teaching method or the incompatibility of the student and teacher at the psychological level. This situation can become a serious obstacle to language learning. English, although an easy language to learn, is not always so easy to learn in reality. Difficulties in each individual case can be caused by different reasons, but in this article I would like to list the most common ones.

The first mistake. Thinking in your native language. It occurs in almost everyone who begins to learn a language and even in those who have been learning it for a long time. The essence is that a person thinks in his native language, translating it into a foreign one. This makes communication difficult and makes phrases too literal and “Russian” (in our case). Learning to overcome the language barrier in your thoughts is extremely important, otherwise you will not be able to speak English fluently.

Mistake two. Incompetence of the teacher. This may include ineffective presentation of material, incorrect pronunciation and accent. Often, English teachers in schools and universities know the language at the level of a scientific linguist, but speak with an accent that students adopt from the very first lessons. Training/communication with native speakers will help you avoid this mistake.

Mistake three. Self-criticism. Setting the bar high and trying to achieve results in the shortest possible time is a sure way to failure. Subsequently, the student loses the desire to learn the language, and he considers himself one of those who are not good at languages. Setting a goal to learn to speak fluently and competently is the right goal, but you need to understand that the results will not be immediate.

Mistake four. Extreme emphasis on grammar. Such an approach can be either a teacher’s mistake or a student’s mistake, who decided that language learning is based on grammar. In fact, memorizing the rules will do little if a person is not able to perceive speech by ear, or does not know how to express himself in a foreign language at all. The process of studying grammar should not be isolated from other processes of language learning, since exclusively “technical” knowledge of the subject does not contribute to speaking a foreign language and overcoming the barrier.

Mistake five. Weak motivation. If a person takes up learning a language under the threat of dismissal or due to possible job privileges, this is not the strongest motivation, since he is pushed to study by certain circumstances, and not by his own desire. In this case, there is no involvement in the learning process, it is uninteresting and the brain subconsciously resists receiving new information.

Mistake six. Neglect of independent learning. Many people are sure that it is enough to turn to a good professional, and he will teach them how to speak. For their part, they consider it quite sufficient to attend classes and be diligent students. But in practice this turns out to be not enough. Without constant self-education (and this includes watching films in English, reading literature, and studying various features of the language, slang, etc.), knowledge of English does not rise to the required level. Again, without interest and complete dedication to the subject, the result will be minimal.

Conclusion

We will consider the main problems and ways to solve them. The main part of the training is devoted to theory, so difficulties arise in using the English language in real life. Solution: after studying the theoretical material, you must immediately apply the acquired knowledge in practice. In percentage terms, you should strive for 30% theory and 70% practice. Many have learned to express their thoughts in English, but cannot comprehend it by ear. Solution: communicate more with native speakers, listen to songs and watch films in English. Mechanical learning of words - "cramming". If you use this method, then after a short time most of the words learned with difficulty will be impossible to remember.

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